

A study on prevalence and associated factors of rotavirus gastroenteritis in children in Western Uttar Pradesh

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Summary

Rotavirus is recognized as a prime causative agent of acute gastroenteritis in children aged less than 5 years worldwide. The aim of this study is to evaluate the frequency of a rotavirus diagnosis in hospitalized children aged less than 5 years suffering from diarrhoea, the efficacy of Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent assay (ELISA) in diagnosing the infection, and assess the relationship between sociodemographic and clinical features associated with rotavirus diarrhea. The present study was conducted at Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College (JNMC), Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh from January 2021 to April 2022. Sociodemographic and clinical data of the patients were assessed. ELISA test was performed for the detection of rotavirus antigen in stool samples.

Statistical analysis was performed using the Prism statistics version 08 software. All the differences were analysed using ANOVA statistical test and Pearson's chi-square (χ^2). According to our results, a total of 382 stool samples were tested and rotavirus infection was detected in 194 (50.7%) samples. Children aged 1-11 months and 12-24 months comprised 56.7% and 18.5% of the total cases respectively. Rotavirus transmission takes place year-round but the infection was significantly higher during winters (n=84, 43.2%) and lower during spring (n=29, 14.9%). Males comprised the majority of positive results (n=127, 65.4%) compared to females (n=67, 34.5%), and were more prone to a positive result compared to females (62% versus 37% respectively). The commonest presenting symptoms were diarrhoea (100%), fever (97.4%), vomiting (92.7%) and severe dehydration (47.4%). In conclusion, rotavirus, a leading cause of gastroenteritis in young children worldwide, was a common cause of fever and diarrhea in our patient series. Although developments in healthcare system have augmented in controlling its prevalence, significant numbers of outbreaks and clusters continue to be recorded in India.

Key words

Rotavirus, ELISA, Prevalence

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Introduction

Rotavirus is an acknowledged prime causative agent of acute gastroenteritis (AGE) in children aged less than 5 years worldwide.¹ Rotavirus gastroenteritis (RVGE) is responsible for approximately 453,000 deaths and 2,400,000 hospitalizations of children aged less than 5 years every year globally.² In Asia in particular, rotavirus is implicated in nearly 45% of hospitalizations due to AGE in children resulting in about 145,000 annual deaths.³ Rotavirus is a member of the *Reoviridae* family characterized by their 11 segmented double-stranded RNA genome. Rotaviruses are classified based on their antigenic properties of outer capsid protein (VP6) in 10 serogroups (A-J); among them rotavirus A is responsible for most viral gastroenteritis cases in

children.⁴ The symptoms associated with rotavirus gastroenteritis are primarily diarrhoea, fever, and in half of all cases vomiting, which may subsequently sometimes lead to severe dehydration.^{5,6} Fever, dehydration and age less than 2 years are important risk factors related with rotavirus diarrhoea.⁷ Rotavirus infection is typically observed in children aged less than 2 years, and particularly in children aged less than 1 year.⁸ The incubation period of rotavirus is 1 to 3 days and symptoms generally last in 3 to 5 days.⁴ Rotavirus transmission primarily occurs by fomites, nearby contacts and fecal-oral route. Numerous research laboratory techniques allow for an easy rotavirus antigen detection in stool samples of children, including enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays, rapid stool antigen detection assays, molecular methods and electron microscopy.⁹

This cross-sectional study of 14 months' duration aimed to evaluate the differences and correlations between clinical and socio-demographical characteristics and rotavirus gastroenteritis. The statistically significant differences of two categorical groups of children were determined by using ANOVA (Analysis of variance) test by testing differences of means using variance. Various variables examined in this study were associated to the rotavirus disease burden of children, including underweight or stunting. Globally, stunting is responsible for more than 3 million deaths every year among children and infants. According to the National Family Health Survey-3 (NFHS-3), malnutrition was a major concern in India with 48% of children having a history of stunting in growth; however in NHFS-4 that percentage was remarkably reduced, to 38.4%.¹⁰

Stunting irreversibly and adversely affects the physical growth, cognitive development, and work productivity of children, and subsequently causes negative long-term consequences.

This study attempts to estimate the rotavirus gastroenteritis specific parameters associated with paediatric diarrheal hospitalizations, in order to augment in implementing proper preventive and effective health care measures in Aligarh region to combat this human health challenge.

Materials and Methods

In our unicentric, prospective surveillance study, stool samples of patients admitted due to acute diarrhea were collected from the paediatric ward of JNMC, and examined at the Viral Research and Diagnosis laboratory (VRDL) (JNMC) AMU, Aligarh from January 2021 to April 2022. All children presenting with more than 3 loose or watery stools within 24 hr period were included in the study. Socio-demographic and clinical characteristics information was obtained using a recorded data collection tool: A questionnaire including age, sex, permanent residence as well as dietary patterns, seasonal patterns, common clinical manifestations including fever, vomiting, duration and frequency of stool and levels of dehydration was used for data collection. Children older than 5 years were excluded from this study, the particular age cut-off was predefined according to rotavirus age susceptibility, ranging from 0 to 60 months. All samples were collected using wide-mouthed sterile plastic containers and stored at -80°C before experimental analysis. The manufacturer's specifications were followed while performing the enzyme immunoassay to detect rotavirus antigen in stool samples.

Data management and statistical analysis: All cal-

culations were executed using the operating system macOS and statistical analysis was performed using the Prism statistics version 08 software. Children positive for rotavirus antigen were compared in terms of clinical and socio-demographical characteristics using the Chi-square test. Differences in severity scores analysis was done by one-way ANOVA (one-way analysis of variance) The outcome was shown as (mean \pm SD) and a p-value of less than or equal to 0.05 is regarded as statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: We conducted a descriptive analysis of stool samples collected only under the ethical guidelines. All protocols were reviewed and approved by the institutional ethics committee of the JNMC, Central Drugs Standard Control Organisation (CDSCO) Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, Government of India with document number (2182/FM and Dated 12/1/2019).

Results

Over all 382 inpatient children with acute diarrhoea were enrolled and tested in this study and the rotavirus infection incidence was 50.7% (194/382). Children aged 2 years or younger accounted for 75.2% of all enrolled cases. The mean age of the enrolled children was 15 months (range 1.4 to 40 months). Rotavirus infection rate in (0-5) months was (n =39, 20.1%), 6-11 months (n=71, 36.5%), 12-23 months (n=36, 18.5%), 24-35 months (n=27, 13.9%), 36-59 months (n=21, 10.8%) (Table 1).

The proportion of positive cases in males (n=127, 65.4%) was higher than females (n=67, 34.5%) which is statistically significant ($P < 0.00001$). Moreover, males were more prone to a positive result (62% of all boys), compared to girls (37% of all girls). Most of the positive cases originated from rural areas (n=113, 58.2%) as compared to urban areas (n=81, 41.7%) but was not statistically significant ($P < .495$); On comparison of feeding of children, rotavirus infection was predominantly observed in children on bottle feed (n=113, 58.2%) compared to breastfeed (n=35, 18%) and this difference exhibited high statistical significance ($P < 0.00001$). The majority of children on bottle-feed were rotavirus positive, while the majority of children on breastfeeding or mixed diet were rotavirus negative. Seasonal assessment of rotavirus positivity showed that rotavirus incidence was high in winter (n=84, 43.2%) followed by summer (n=47, 24.2%), autumn (n=34, 17.5%) and spring (n=29, 14.9%) and this association between seasonal patterns and rotavirus infection was statistically significant ($P < .05$) (Table 1). The distribution of rotavirus incidence according to

Table 1 Peer grouping of admitted children suffered from AGE (n=382) and positive for RV (n=194).

Age Group	Number of children admitted with AGE	Number of RV +ve (% of all RV +ve)	Number of RV -ve (% of all RV -ve)	% of RV +ve by age group
0-5	62	39 (20.1%)	23 (12.2%)	62.90
6-11	110	71 (36.5%)	39 (20.7%)	64.54
2-23	92	36 (18.5%)	56 (29.7%)	39.13
24-35	64	27 (13.9%)	37 (19.6%)	42.18
36-59	54	21 (10.8%)	33 (17.5%)	38.88
Total	382	194	188	50.78

Figure 1 Seasonality of rotavirus gastroenteritis.

different seasons of the year is depicted in Figure 1.

The study showed that the children with a positive rotavirus test commonly presented with fever (n=189, 97.4%) and vomiting (n=180, 92.7%), in a highly statistically significant manner (P<0.00001). Differences in the duration of diarrhoea were observed, ≤3 days (n=76, 39.1%), ≤6 days (n=63, 32.4%), >6 days (n=55, 28.3%) but were non-significant (P<.345). Association of dehydration status with rotavirus positivity among children was also assessed, with 11.8% of the children suffering from mild dehydration, while 47.4% suffered from severe dehydration, a trend that was highly statistically significant (P< 0.005). In comparison of un-

derweight, stunting and wasting among children, underweight (n=63, 32.4%) and wasting (n=29, 14.9%) differ significantly while stunting (n=102, 52.5%) was significantly highest. Association of nutritional status with rotavirus positivity showed that rotavirus gastroenteritis rate was observed in the majority of stunted children but not in the majority of underweight and wasted ones, and this was statistically significant (P<.0082) (Table 3).

Discussion

This study aimed to determine the prevalence of rota-

Table 2 Sociodemographic characteristics of children suffering from acute gastroenteritis (n=382).

Characteristics		Rotavirus positive (n=194)	Rotavirus negative (n=188)	χ^2	P value
Age (Months)	0 – 5	39 (20.1%)	23 (12.2%)	21.9263	.000207
	6 –11	71 (36.5%)	39 (20.7%)		
	12-23	36 (18.5%)	56 (29.7%)		
	24-35	27 (13.9%)	37 (19.6%)		
	36-59	21 (10.8%)	33 (17.5%)		
Gender	Male	127 (65.4%)	73 (38.8%)	27.1518	<0.00001
	Female	67 (34.5%)	115 (61.1%)		
Residence	Rural	113 (58.2%)	103 (54.7%)	00.4652	.495193
	Urban	81 (41.7%)	85 (45.2%)		
Diet patterns	Only Bottle feed	113 (58.2%)	52 (27.6%)	36.5151	<0.00001
	Bottle+Breastfeed	46 (23.7%)	74 (39.3%)		
	Only Breast feed	35 (18%)	62 (32.9%)		
Seasonal patterns	Spring	29 (14.9%)	78 (41.4%)	45.7782	<0.00001
	Summer	47 (24.2%)	43 (22.8%)		
	Autumn	34 (17.5%)	39 (20.7%)		
	Winter	84 (43.2%)	28 (14.8%)		

virus disease and to assess the relationship between the sociodemographic and clinical features associated with children presenting with acute gastroenteritis in Aligarh region of western Uttar Pradesh and a positive rotavirus diagnosis. In the present study rotavirus was detected to be a major enteropathogen and found period prevalence of rotavirus infection was 50.7%. Global surveillance networks reported a prevalence of rotavirus gastroenteritis ranging from 6 to 56% among children and infants hospitalized with viral diarrhoea.¹¹ Our findings are similar to previous studies, where rotavirus prevalence of 45% and 46.2% was reported.¹² Contrary to our study, other authors have reported lower rotavirus prevalence ranging from 7.4% to 28.15% in various states of India.^{13,14} The result of our study showed that rotavirus frequency was higher in the age range of 6-11 and 12-23 months, similar to what has been reported previously.^{15,16} This study reveals that interrelationships exist between the age group and rotavirus outbreaks, maximum infections occurring in children of 6-11 months.^{17,18} Other studies

have reported that the incidence of rotavirus diarrhoea was higher in children aged less than 2 years in contrast to those between 2-5 years of age, in full agreement with our study.¹⁹ The reduction in prevalence of rotavirus infections after aged 2 years may imply that most children have already contacted rotavirus antigens at early age and have developed immunity. Major clinical symptoms of RVGE in our study were fever (97.4%) and vomiting (92.7%) as previous research stated.^{20,21} Vomiting has always been a prevalent occurrence in rotavirus diarrhoea, and has been documented to occur in almost half of all rotavirus diarrhoea cases.²² Rotavirus activity is high typically during the winter season, starting in late autumn and lasting until the spring.^{23,24} Previous studies have found that rotavirus infection was most common in temperate countries during the winter months, while year-round trends were common in tropical places. India is a tropical country and rotavirus infection was found year round in this study but was higher in winter months.²⁵ Our study revealed that children with rota-

Table 3 Comparative profile of clinical features among acute gastroenteritis patients with and without rotavirus infection.

Characteristics		Rotavirus positive (n=194)	Rotavirus negative (n=188)	χ^2	P value
Fever		189 (97.4%)	68 (36.1%)	33.1308	<.00001
Vomiting		180 (92.7%)	73 (38.8%)	26.0639	<.00001
Duration of Diarrhea in days	1-3	76 (39.1%)	69 (36.7%)	2.1274	.345172
	4-6	63 (32.4%)	74 (39.3%)		
	<6	55 (28.3%)	45 (23.9%)		
Stool Consistency	Semi-Liquid	71 (36.5%)	143 (76%)	7.2389	.007134
	Liquid	123 (63.4%)	45 (23.9%)		
Stool color	Pale	54 (27.8%)	82 (43.6%)	12.5057	.001925
	Green	78 (40.2%)	49 (26%)		
	Yellow	62 (31.9%)	57 (30.3%)		
Loose Stool frequency in past 24 h	1-3 times	54 (27.8%)	73 (38.8%)	5.2158	.073687
	4-7 times	78 (40.2%)	64 (34%)		
	>7 times	62 (31.9%)	51 (27.1%)		
Mucous Dehydration (Degree)	Present	57 (29.3%)	34 (18%)	4.145	.041758
	Mild	23 (11.8%)	85 (45.2%)		
	Moderate	79 (40.7%)	58 (30.8%)		
	Severe	92 (47.4%)	45 (23.9%)		
Malnutrition	Underweight	63 (32.4%)	72 (37.1%)	9.6164	.008162
	Stunted	102 (52.5%)	69 (36.7%)		
	Wasted	29 (14.9%)	47 (25%)		

virus infection had a longer duration of diarrhoea and were more susceptible to severe dehydration (47.4%) than children without a rotavirus diagnosis (23.9%). This finding validated previous studies which showed that dehydration was a significant characteristic of rotavirus diarrhoea.^{26,27} The current study found and confirmed that an important risk factor associated with acute diarrhoea in children aged less than 5 years is the type of feeding in initial days of life. When comparing types of feeding in rotavirus-positive children, we found that only 18% were breastfed infants as compared to 58.2% of infants dependent on bottle feeding. Moreover, breastfed children with diarrhoea had a 36% positivity rate of rotavirus diagnosis, infants with a mixed feeding formula (both breastfed and bottle-fed) had a 38.3% positivity rate, compared to bottle-fed

children, who exhibited a 68.4% rotavirus positivity rate. This finding adds to previous observations that viral diarrhoea is less common in infants who were breastfed compared to bottle-fed infants.^{28,29} Previous studies have shown that in 0–6 months there was remarkable reduction of rotavirus-antigenemia in the serum of breast-fed infants compared to non-breast-fed infants.³⁰ Antigenemia is a common event among children associated with severe acute gastroenteritis and specifies the presence of rotavirus antigen in the serum of blood. Studies have shown that children who rely on breast milk had lower risk of rotavirus gastroenteritis, probably due to the protective effect of IgA which is found abundantly in breast milk.³¹ In our study, rotavirus positive children were predominantly male (65.4%), and male children were more prone to

a positive rotavirus diagnosis in general. This finding is similar to the results of previous studies showing that rotavirus infection was higher in male children compared to female children.^{32,33} The reasons for this difference of rotavirus infection incidence between males and females are not known.³⁴⁻³⁶

Our study showed no significant difference in prevalence of AGE in terms of rural (58.2%) and urban locations (41.7%), since positivity rates were close to overall residence rates. High population density and close contact have been incriminated for increased incidences and spread of rotavirus infection among children. However improvements in water and hygienic variables have been shown as efficacious measures for prevention of rotavirus infection. In this study we perceived that 85% of paediatric patients, who suffered from rotavirus lived in densely populated rural or urban locality. Previous studies reported that overcrowding plays vital role for community based circulation of rotavirus infection.^{37,38} The association of nutritional status with rotavirus positivity was also evaluated. It clearly showed that rotavirus prevalence differs between underweight (32.4%) and stunted (52.5%) children, also there was high difference between stunted and wasted (14.9%) children. Overall though, stunted children were prone to rotavirus positivity than underweight and wasted children. In India and particularly in Uttar Pradesh studies about malnutrition are absent.³⁹ However few studies have confirmed the robust association between diminished growth and rotavirus.⁴⁰

A 2019 study estimates that every year rotavirus causes 78,500 deaths, 872,000 hospitalizations, and 3.2 million outpatient cases in India.⁴¹ Previous studies have shown that India accounts for 22% of the total mortality occurring due to rotavirus worldwide.⁴² According to a CDC report, oral vaccines of rotavirus (Rotateq and Rotarix recommended by WHO) are an exquisite prophylaxis from rotaviral diarrhoea in 4 out of 5 children during their infancy. Worldwide rotavirus vaccination has emerged as a preventive weapon, and till now more than 107 countries have introduced their use, resulting in drastic reductions of mortality and morbidity. India became one of the first countries in the World Health Organization (WHO) Southeast Asia region to introduce an indigenously manufactured rotavirus vaccine (RVV) in the Universal Immunization Program.⁴³ The government of India had introduced rotavirus oral vaccine (Rotavac) in 2016 in a phased manner starting with 4 states i.e, Odisha, Andhra Pradesh, Haryana, and Himachal Pradesh and later, it expanded in 2017 to other states.⁴⁴ In July 2018, the introduction of phase 3 program of rotavirus vaccination was initiated in Uttar Pradesh, India.⁴⁵ De-

spite these widespread vaccination programs, rotavirus is still a leading causative agent of AGE in young children in Uttar Pradesh. For considerable reduction of rotavirus burden, WHO proposed rotavirus vaccination as the effective master plan to be incorporated in all national immunization programs (NIPs), particularly in countries which report high rotavirus gastroenteritis related morbidity and mortality.

The strengths of this study include, that it was the first relevant study in Aligarh district, specifically detecting the burden of rotavirus disease in children with acute diarrhoea. However, the present study has some limitations, since it was conducted exclusively in hospitalized children with acute gastroenteritis, hence the outcome is not likely to be representative of the magnitude of viral diarrhea in the population. Also authors have not consider other diarrhea causing pathogens. This study further outlined the relationship of rotavirus diarrhea with stunting and malnutrition. Improved hygiene, healthy nourishment and implementation of rotavirus vaccination in the community should be public health priorities in India.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study highlights that rotavirus is a principal causing agent of diarrheal disease among children aged 3-24 months in Aligarh district in Uttar Pradesh. The burden of rotavirus associated diarrhoea was high during the cold dry season with significant risk of fever, vomiting and severe dehydration. The prevalence of rotavirus infection was high among children who did not breastfeed. The strategy for rotavirus infection control includes taking measures towards rotavirus vaccination and improved hygiene and sanitation in the community.

Conflict of interest statements

The authors declared they do not have anything to disclose about the conflict of interest concerning this manuscript.

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Institutional Ethics Committee Statement: The project was approved and examined by members of the Institutional Ethics Committee of the Indian Institute of Public Health, New Delhi-110017-India.

Institutional Review Board statement: No need.

Informed Consent Statement: No need. The stool samples were collected based on a patient's illness. The patients were not treated to any medical procedure (Surgery) or any medical experiment, nor prescribed drugs before and after the experimental study. So patient health risks/benefits or similar not associated with this study.

Consent for publication: Yes, the authors declared consent for publication

Declarations

Author contribution:

Protocol/project development:

Haris Manzoor Khan, Sadia Saher

Data collection or management:

Sadia Saher, Zeeshan Mustafa Khan, Syed Gazanfar ali

Data analysis: *Sadia Saher, Hiba Sami*

Manuscript writing/editing: *Sadia Saher*

The results of the Chi-square tests should be provided in an APA reference style:

I have done my statistical analysis of Chi-Square test through online calculator

<https://www.socscistatistics.com> > tests > chisquare

Περίληψη

A study on prevalence and associated factors of rotavirus gastroenteritis in children in Western Uttar Pradesh

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Οι ροταϊοί αποτελούν μείζονα αιτιολογικό παράγοντα της οξείας γαστρεντερίτιδας σε παιδιά ηλικίας κάτω των 5 ετών παγκοσμίως. Σκοπός αυτής της μελέτης ήταν η εκτίμηση της συχνότητας μόλυνσης από ροταϊό των νοσηλευόμενων παιδιών ηλικίας κάτω των 5 ετών με κλινική εικόνα διάρροιας, της αποτελεσματικότητας των ενζυμικών ανοσολογικών τεχνικών (ELISA) στη διάγνωση της λοίμωξης και η αξιολόγηση της συσχέτισης μεταξύ των κοινωνικο-δημογραφικών και κλινικών χαρακτηριστικών που σχετίζονται με τη διάρροια από ροταϊούς. Η μελέτη διεξήχθη στο Jawahar Lal Nehru Medical College (JNMC), Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh από τον Ιανουάριο του 2021 έως τον Απρίλιο του 2022. Αξιολογήθηκαν κοινωνικο-δημογραφικά και κλινικά δεδομένα των ασθενών. Πραγματοποιήθηκε δοκιμή ELISA για την ανίχνευση αντιγόνου ροταϊού σε δείγματα κοπράνων. Η στατιστική ανάλυση έγινε χρησιμοποιώντας το λογισμικό Prism statistics έκδοση 08. Όλες οι διαφορές αναλύθηκαν χρησιμοποιώντας το στατιστικό τεστ ANOVA και το chi-square Pearson (X²). Σύμφωνα με τα αποτελέσματά μας, εξετάστηκαν συνολικά 382 δείγματα κοπράνων και ανιχνεύθηκε μόλυνση από ροταϊούς σε 194 (50,7%) δείγματα. Τα παιδιά ηλικίας 1-11 μηνών και 12-24 μηνών αποτελούσαν το 56,7% και το 18,5% του συνόλου των περιπτώσεων αντίστοιχα. Η μετάδοση του ροταϊού γίνεται όλο το χρόνο, αλλά η μόλυνση ήταν σημαντικά υψηλότερη κατά τους χειμώνες (n=84, 43,2%) και χαμηλότερη την άνοιξη (n=29, 14,9%). Αγόρια αποτελούσαν την πλειοψηφία των θετικών διαγνώσεων (n=127, 65,4%) σε σύγκριση με κορίτσια (n=67, 34,5%), ενώ εμφάνιζαν και μεγαλύτερη πιθανότητα θετικής διάγνωσης σε σχέση με κορίτσια (62% έναντι 37%). Τα πιο κοινά συμπτώματα που καταγράφηκαν ήταν διάρροια (100%), πυρετός (97,4%), έμετος (92,7%) και σοβαρή αφυδάτωση (47,4%). Συμπερασματικά, η λοίμωξη από ροταϊούς, μείζον αίτιο γαστρεντερίτιδας μικρών παιδιών παγκοσμίως, αποτέλεσε συχνό αίτιο πυρετού και διάρροιας στην παρούσα σειρά ασθενών. Αν και η πρόοδος των συστημάτων υγείας έχει συμβάλει στον έλεγχο της επίπτωσής της, σημαντικός αριθμός συρροών και μικρο-επιδημιών συνεχίζει να καταγράφεται στην Ινδία.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

Ροταϊός, ELISA, επιπολασμός

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